

ETHYLENE OXIDE GAS STERILIZATION: AN EVIDENCE-BASED REVIEW OF HISTORY, PROPERTIES, APPLICATIONS, AND CLINICAL IMPACT"

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Abstract

Ethylene oxide is a familiar sterilizing agent that is used to sterilize different surgical items that are heat, moisture, and radiosensitive. Ethylene oxide gas was first time prepared by Wurtz. Due to its advantages and ease of use, nowadays it has become a familiar sterilization technique in the medical and pharmaceutical fields. Its worldwide production is 5.5 million tons. Ethylene oxide is a colorless liquid that has a boiling point of 10.7 centigrade and highly explosive and flammable. It is also toxic for humans because it can cause mutations. Ethylene oxide is an antibacterial agent and it is used to kill viruses, spores, and different microorganisms. It has the ability of alkylation reaction due to its ability can bind with DNA, nucleic acid-protein, and enzymes and result in the denaturation or killing of the microorganisms. Sterilization requires the removal of all water and lubricants because ethylene oxide oxide gas can react with this and make a toxic residue. Microsurgical instruments require special handling because they can be easily damaged. The packing material should be made up of woven and non-woven fabrics, and it should be lint-free. It cannot produce contamination upon opening the pack. Various types of biological and chemical indicators are used to check whether the instruments are properly sterilized or not. Chemical indicators were a special type of paper that changed their color when they were exposed to ethylene oxide. The biological indicators are the spores of special types of organisms that are placed in the sterilizer unit. In the future due to its advantages and its better effectiveness against bacteria, viruses, and spores is probably the most used method, but it also required some special care during its handling and usage due to its toxic effects.

INTRODUCTION

Annual production of ethylene oxide is 0.24%, which is approximately equal to 7 million kg. Firstly, it is used for, the manufacturing of medical devices and

secondly, it is used to sterilize the instruments, equipment, and supplies in the hospital (1). Worldwide production of Ethylene oxide is 5.5

million tonnes and in the United States is 3 million tonnes (2). It's 60% is used for the preparation of ethylene glycol, 12% is used for the production of non-ionic surfactants, and in less percentage, it is used to produce glycol ethers, ethanolamine, and other chemicals (3). In the medical field, it is used for fumigation of the operation theater and other medical products (4).

Ethylene oxide is prepared with the help of the procedure of chlorohydrin process. Ethylene oxide was first prepared by Wurtz in 1859 (5). He Discovered ethylene oxide when he performed a reaction on potassium hydroxide with ethylene chlorohydrin. In this reaction, Wurtz prepared the ethylene oxide from ethylene chlorohydrin. In this method for the preparation of ethylene oxide gas, he took the 6-8% concentrated solution of chlorohydrin, and this solution is mixed with the water-based suspension known as a lime slurry of 10- 15% calcium oxide concentration. After this, he gives the heat to this prepared mixture for a few minutes to speed up this reaction. Then this reacted mixture is placed on a destructive distillation at some distance. After these operations had been completed, he selected the open steam and placed it near the bottom of the destructive distillation column. Then a tiny volume of caustic solution or lime slurry to the mixture to impact the saponification of untreated chlorohydrin. Which can be overcome with crude oxide. He prepared the ethylene oxide gas by removing hydrochloric acid from ethylene chlorohydrin with the help of using potassium hydroxide solution.

In 1914 the Industrial production of Ethylene oxide with the help of chlorohydrin is begun, and this preparation of ethylene oxide worked on the principle of Wurtz, 's discovery (6). In 1932, Lefort discovered a new process for producing ethylene oxide, which he called direct oxidation of ethylene in the presence of a catalyst (7). The catalysts that were placed in the tubes were in the form of spheres and rings. This method used a recycled gas stream that is circulated in the reactor through the compressor. In this method, he used a mixture of ethylene and air. This mixture is passed through a tube that contained a silver catalyst the temperature of this tube is maintained with the help of the reactor in the range of between 200 to 350 centigrade. The reactor is a bundle of tubes. These tubes are 6-13m long and have an internal diameter of

20-50mm. The temperature of the reactor depends upon the type of catalyst used. The result of this gas-liquid contains carbon dioxide, nitrogen, unreacted ethylene, oxygen, and ethylene oxide (8).

Ethylene oxide is discovered as an antibacterial agent. It has a reactive nature and a colorless liquid. It has a boiling point of 10.7 centigrade and above this temperature it has a character of an ethereal smell (9). That is an inflammable gas with the characteristic of simplest epoxide compounds and portent biocide. If the concentration of ethylene oxide is higher than 3% it becomes explosive and moderately toxic. Due to its reactive nature, it is a major industrial chemical. Its toxicity is comparable to ammonia. The 12% mixture of ethylene oxide with carbon dioxide and freons is not inflammable. It is an alkylating agent and readily soluble in water rubber, and many plastics. It is a dominant sterilizing agent that is used to sterilize all the medical supplies, instruments, and equipment that were heat, moisture, and radiosensitive (10). It is widely used due to its effective characteristics and compatibility with the materials. On the other hand, ethylene oxide has many disadvantages due to its toxic effects. It required special care and handling for the usage of ethylene oxide. If it is used in a place where no proper ventilation system is available, it becomes toxic for the workers. It can affect their central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, and reproductive system. Ethylene oxide can cause different diseases such as Leukemia, cytotoxicity, and chromosomal damage (11). Nowadays there are two methods used for sterilizing instruments, equipment, and supplies from ethylene oxide gas. These methods are the pre-vacuum sterilization method and the non-vacuum sterilization method (12). In the pre-vacuum sterilization method, the air is first removed from the sterilizer chamber and then ethylene oxide gas is injected into the sterilizer. While in the non-vacuumed sterilization method air was not removed from the chamber and the cycle proceeded.

Ethylene oxide gas sterilizer unit

Ethylene oxide gas sterilization depends upon these parameters.

1. Concentration of ethylene oxide gas
2. Temperature
3. Humidity
4. Time

1. Concentration of ethylene oxide gas

Ethylene oxide gas is supplied in liquid form in the metallic cylinder and disposable cartridges. It is used in the sterilization process in its pure form and in some cases in diluted forms is also used. Phillips in 1949 says that the concentration of ethylene oxide gas and the time were inversely proportional to each other. If we double the amount of ethylene oxide gas it decreases the half of the time required for the sterilization. So, the conclusion found that if we increased the concentration of ethylene oxide gas it can decreased the time required for the sterilization process (13). There are some forms of ethylene oxide gases that can be used in the sterilization cycle (14)

1. CFC-12

This is also known as 12/88. CFC-12 is a mixture of ethylene oxide gas and chlorofluorocarbon. In this mixture, the concentration of ethylene oxide gas is 12% and chlorofluorocarbon is 88% (15). Chlorofluorocarbon is harmful to the ozone layer so that, why it is not recommended.

2. HCFC-124

It has a trade name of Oxyfume 2000. This form of ethylene oxide gas is also used to sterilized the instruments.

3. EO/CO₂

It is also known as 10/90. It is a mixture of 10% ethylene oxide gas and 90% carbon dioxide, this mixture is not 100% efficient in sterilizing all medical devices because there is a high-pressure difference between ethylene oxide and carbon dioxide so it was very difficult to maintain a homogeneous mixture of these gases (16).

4. 100%EO

It is 67 g or 134 g pure ethylene oxide that is used in this sterilization cycle. Ethylene oxide gas in its pure form is highly explosive so, it required special attention in handling and usage.

2. Temperature

The temperature also affects this sterilization cycle. Temperature can increased the destruction of microorganisms by giving permeability to ethylene oxide gas to invade the cell wall of microorganisms

and into the packing material in which instruments are placed. These sterilizers are operated in the temperature range of 85F to 145F (17). If we increase the temperature of the sterilizer, it can decrease the time required for the sterilization. The temperature of the sterilizer is increased by injecting saturated steam into the chamber of the sterilizer.

3. Humidity

Humidity is necessary to achieve sterilization with ethylene oxide gas. Some endospores are highly resistant to ethylene oxide gas sterilization because their outer covering is highly dried and resistant to moisture. The moisture content of the sterilizer and the water content of the organism itself is important for the action of ethylene oxide gas on the microorganism and spores to kill. 20% to 40% humidity is necessary to kill the microorganism by ethylene oxide (18). It is important to maintain the humidity level of the sterilizer unit in which the items were prepared and packed for sterilization. The humidity of this sterilizer unit should be maintained in the range of 30 to 80% throughout the sterilization cycle. The quality of the items and their packing material to observe the moisture also affect the sterilization (19). Also, keep in mind that excessive humidity can inhibit the sterilization cycle. At any place where the water is present, it means that the item was not sterilized properly. Pre-humidification of the packing material before exposing the ethylene oxide increased the penetration of the water in the packing material which decreased the time for the sterilization.

4. Time

It is the time required for the destruction of all types of lives on the. Temperature, concentration of ethylene oxide gas, the arrangement of items in the sterilizer, types of material, and the cleanness of the items are all factors that depends upon the time required for the sterilization.

Mechanism of action of ethylene oxide

Due to the strong reactivity of ethylene oxide, it is critical for microorganism inactivation. This strong reactivity of ethylene oxide is measured by the exergonic combustion reaction with the combination of high diffusivity. Ethylene oxide is a direct-acting

alkylating agent that does not require metabolic activation to kill the microorganisms (20). Ethylene oxide has the ability to alkylation reaction with DNA, nucleic acids, protein, and enzymes that result in the denaturation of the microorganisms. The binding of the alkyl group to the Sulfhydryl, hydroxyl amino, and carboxyl group on protein, DNA, and RNA in the microorganisms stops the normal reproduction mechanism and cellular metabolism.

Preparation of the items for sterilization

All the items that required sterilization are thoroughly cleaned and dried. Remove all the water from the instruments and equipment because ethylene oxide can react with this water and make a toxic residue that is harmful when anyone is in contact with this (21). Items are placed loosely in the sterilizer for the penetration of the gas and not placed too tight. Make a set of similar items that have the same aeration requirements. Complex instruments are disassembled prior to the sterilization so, that the gas are exposed to all parts(22). Placed sharps instruments separately in the serializer to prevent injury. Any instruments that have a lumen should be completely dried by introducing air into the lumen. Removed all the lubricants from the instruments prior to sterilization because ethylene oxide cannot penetrate into the lubricants. Placed heavy instruments in the bottom of the sterilizer. Inspection of all the items is necessary prior to the sterilization to check whether he is in working condition or not. All the instrument's ratchet and jaws remained open in the instrument pack for the penetration of the ethylene oxide gas (23). Microsurgical instruments require special handling and care because they can be easily damaged. Microsurgical instruments were placed in a special tray that had molded plastic mats in its bottom (24). The weight of the instrument should not exceed more than 16 pounds. Instrument trays and containers placed horizontally are flat in the sterilizer. Ethylene oxide does not penetrate into the glass so the solution in the glass boils are bottles cannot be sterilized by ethylene oxide. Some pharmaceutical items and acrylics cannot be sterilized by ethylene oxide (25). In the bottom of the instrument try nonwoven wrapper cannot be placed because it can produce moisture that can affect the sterilization. Instruments are placed in rods and

secured with clips to maintain the instrument's Jaws, ratchets, and cutting blades in an open position. Instruments that have concave surfaces required special attention because water and air were trapped in the concave surfaces of these instruments. Prevents the instruments from metal-to-metal contact because this affects the coating of the instruments. The wrapping technique of the instruments for ethylene oxide gas sterilization is the same as steam sterilization. Nylon, Rayon, PVC, and polyester are not used in ethylene oxide gas sterilization. The double-wrapping technique of instruments is not suitable for ethylene oxide gas sterilization. Always follow the manufacturer's instructions to prepare the items for ethylene oxide sterilization. Some paper wrappers range from kraft to permanent and crepe are also used for ethylene oxide gas sterilization.

Characteristics of packing material

Packing material should have the ability to allow ethylene oxide gas to penetrate the wrapper and reach out to all surfaces of the instrument for sterilization. It does not produce toxic ingredients. The packing material should be lint-free. It should be large enough that he can enclose all the surfaces of the instrument. It should be strong enough for storage and handling. It should be convenient and easily handleable. It should not produce contamination on opening the pack. The packing material should have maximum uses. The packing material should allow easy opening and closing and the ability to remove air from its wrapper. It should have the ability to bear high temperature, pressure, and humidity and allow aeration from the packing material at the end of the sterilization cycle. It should have resistance to tears and punctures. The packing material has the ability to not be easily degradable because some items require storage after sterilization. Packing material should have the ability to resist the penetration of dust and unwanted particles. Dyes should not be present on the packing material because they can cause discoloration of the items (26). Packing material must allow for the seal to remain intact in order to maintain the sterility of the pack. All the instruments equipment and supplies that required sterilization were properly wrapped in a standard packing material that was suitable according to the sterilization method. The purpose of this packing material was to prevent the

instruments from contamination, after the sterilization. There are two types of packing material are commonly used for packing woven and non-woven paper (21). The size, shape, type, and thickness of the packing material affect the penetration time of ethylene oxide gas. Items that are to be sterilized for ethylene oxide gas should be separately tagged so these items do not mix with other items that require steam or radiation sterilization. Nylon, PVC, polyester, polyvinyl alcohol, cellophane, Aluminum foil, and a combination of these materials are not used for ethylene oxide gas sterilization, because it does not allow the penetration of the gases.

Woven fabric

Reusable double-thickness woven fabric is used for ethylene oxide gas sterilization. Woven wrappers are made up of a combination of cotton and polyester. These wrappers are strong enough that they can protect the instruments from contamination and it has porous allowed the penetration of the gas. 140 threads are present in one inch of the woven fabric. Before sterilization, it is necessary to remove all the debris from the wrappers so, that it could not cause contamination. Inspection of the wrappers for tears and pinholes is necessary before sterilization. The woven wrappers can absorb the large amount of humidity that is necessary for the action of ethylene oxide (27).

Non-woven fabrics

Tyvek spun, bonded olefin and high-density polyethylene allowed a complete penetration of the ethylene oxide gas and moisture. These fabric packs are disposable. These packs are single and double-wrapped according to the material specification (28). Non-woven wrappers are only the single time useable. These wrappers are made up of spun and polypropylene and are used for heavy instruments that have a flat surface such as trays, basins, and linen packs (29).

Peel packs and pouches

Double wrapping of the instruments does not allow good access to the penetration of ethylene oxide through the instrument. These pouches are either coated or uncoated. These pouches allowed visualization of the instruments within the pack. Peel

pouches are made up of synthetic materials such as Tyvek (30). Aeration cycle after ethylene oxide gas sterilization. Ethylene oxide can produce toxic residues after the sterilization cycle so it is necessary to aerate the items before using it. That is necessary because these toxic residuals are harmful to the patients, workers, and everyone who is exposed to them. The aeration cycle is performed in a special room under the controlled recommended conditions. Aeration time depends on the following conditions. Composition and property of the material, designated area in which sterilization cycle is performed, packing material of the instruments and sterilizing conditions such as temperature pressure time humidity and size of the load. The temperature, airflow pattern in the sterilizer unit, and thickness of the wall of the item affect the removal of ethylene oxide gas residuals from the product (31). Nowadays different aeration technologies are also available for the removal of the residuals from the instrument, equipment, and supplies that are sterilized with ethylene oxide gas. These technologies are pulsed vacuum post-process, steam addition, heat addition, and microwave absorption. The residual amount of ethylene oxide gas is measured by dividing the weight of ethylene oxide gas residuals that were remaining on the item by the original weight of the item. The aeration cycle is performed in the well-ventilated and cleaned area.

Advantages of ethylene oxide gas sterilization method

Ethylene oxide is used to sterilize the items that are heat and water-sensitive. Steam and gamma radiations can change the physical and mechanical properties of the polymers, but ethylene oxide cannot change these properties. It is used in the medical, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. Ethylene oxide is an ideal sterilizing agent that has a property of high diffusivity and has high compatibility with most materials (32). It has a microbicidal, and viricidal fungicidal activity and a powerful alkylating agent. Ethylene oxide was used in a special type of controlled environment that was fire-resistant.

Disadvantages of ethylene oxide gas

Ethylene oxide gas is toxic and inflammable. It has a harmful effect on humans, environment, and required a large designated working area. The

sterilization cycle is lengthy and took several hours. It required special care during handling and usage and produced toxic residuals during the sterilization cycle. Due to its toxic and inflammable properties ethylene oxide is a more complex procedure than any other sterilization type (33). Ethylene oxide can produce blistering on the skin and on the mucous membrane and can cause serious burns on the skin if it is not properly handled. If the exposure of ethylene oxide is prolonged it can cause mutation and leukemia in the exposed person (21).

Monitoring of the sterilization cycle

Various industrial methods are present to check whether the instruments are properly sterilized or not. Some methods are the use of strips, paper indicators, and some of the usage of spores of different microorganisms that are placed inside the sterilizer. A quality checkup is an important component of the sterilization process to check the sterilization of the instrument. To prevent surgical site infection and enhance patient safety and care the surgical instruments must be properly sterilized. There are various methods present to check the sterilization cycle(17).

1. Mechanical

2. Chemical

3. Biological

There are some types of modern sterilizers present to check the sterilization process. These sterilizers have microprocessors that give detailed feedback on each cycle of the sterilization.

1. Mechanical indicators

The ethylene oxide gas machine is equipped with different gauges that were used to monitor the time, temperature, concentration, and humidity of ethylene oxide gas that required for proper sterilization. In some sterilization units, some people used charts to note down these parameters. Nowadays some ethylene oxide gas machines themselves produce the digital record of time, temperature, concentration of ethylene oxide gas, and humidity. After that, the person who operated these machines checked these parameters and verified the sterilization cycle (34).

2. Chemical indicators

Chemical indicators are placed externally and internally in the instrumentation box. The color of these chemical indicators showed that instruments are exposed to specific temperature, humidity, and sterilizing agents (35). These chemical indicators are the special types of papers that change color when they are exposed to ethylene oxide gas (36). The most common types of these indicators were autoclave tapes that were placed outside and inside the instrumentation box. The internal indicator is placed at which place where there are high chances of the interaction of the air. The color of the tape was cream with the presence of diagonal lines. After that when the ethylene oxide gas was exposed to it the color of diagonal lines was changed from red to yellow. The 4-(4-nitro benzyl) pyridine was a sensitive reagent for the detection of alkylating agents. When this reagent is exposed to ethylene oxide gas it produced a methine dye that has a blue color in an alkaline medium. 4-(nitrobenzyl) pyridine is used in the laboratory for the detection of ethylene oxide gas in the solutions and is also used as the exposure indicator to detect the ethylene oxide gas. The color of this indicator strip was turned into a blue color when they were exposed to ethylene oxide (37).

3. Biological indicators

A biological indicator system is used to check the sterilization of pharmaceutical and medical devices. Chemical indicators are very sensitive to ethylene oxide gas even if they can change their color with the exposure of a very small amount of ethylene oxide gas so this problem gives the idea of a biological indicators system. The biological indicators system is the most accurate method to check the parameters of the sterilization cycle (38). For this, bacterial endospores such as *Bacillus Subtilis*, *B. Atrophies*, and *B. Stearothermophilus* are more resistant to sterilization and are placed inside the vial. The spores of *B. Atrophies* were the suggested biological indicator to check the sterilization. The vial is placed in the central part of the sterilization pack where the penetration of the gas is very difficult. After the completion of this cycle, the vial is removed and the bacteria were encultured to check the bacterial growth. If all the parameters of the sterilization were not met then the spores cannot germinate. If the spores germinate then

this sterilization cycle is not complete and the instrument requires reesterilization (39).

Discussion

The ethylene oxide gas sterilization method was the most appropriate method to sterilize all the items that are moisture, heat, and radiosensitive. It was a colorless gas that was converted into a liquid at a low temperature and readily soluble in water and organic solvents. It was exclusive and had a harmful effect on the human central nervous system, reproductive, and peripheral nervous system. It was carcinogenic and mutagenic in humans (40). That why its required special care and attention during handling. Its worldwide production is 5.5 million tonnes and 60% was used to prepare ethylene glycol 12% was used for the manufacturing of non-ionic surfactants and in a very small amount it was used to produce glycol ethers, ethanalamine, and other chemicals. It was most widely used in the chemical industry and in the medical industry. It was used to sterilize instruments, equipment, supplies, and the fumigation of the operation theatre (31). It was supplied in metallic cylinders and disposable cartridges and has different forms that were used in the sterilization cycle such as HCFC124, 100% ethylene oxide, etc. Ethylene oxide is an antibacterial agent due to its ability can kill bacteria, viruses, and spores (41). It was an alkylating agent due to its alkylating ability ethylene oxide reacts with DNA, nucleic acid, protein, and enzymes of the microorganisms and causes its denaturation. By binding the alkyl group to the Sulfhydryl, hydroxyl amino, and the carboxyl group of protein, DNA, and RNA of the microorganism. It can stop the normal reproduction mechanism and cellular metabolism of the microorganisms resulting in their cellular death. The sterilization cycle depends upon the concentration of ethylene oxide gas, temperature, humidity, and time. If doubled the amount of the concentration of ethylene oxide it could decrease by half of the time required for the sterilization, with the help of increasing the temperature of the sterilizer the time required for the sterilization was decreased (42). Before the ethylene oxide gas sterilization, all the items need necessary decontamination. Removed all the water, and oil lubricants from the instruments because these can produce toxic residues. Complex instruments were disassembled before sterilization

heavy instruments in the bottom and the lighter instruments on the top of the try. Packing material must be lint-free, not produce toxic residues, must be environmentally friendly, and cannot produce contamination on the opening of the pack (43). Ethylene oxide gas produces toxic residuals so all the instruments after the sterilization need an aeration cycle for the removal of toxic residue (44). The aeration time depends upon the composition and property of the material, the area of the sterilization cycle, the packing material of the instruments, and the size of the load. All the instruments that are sterilized require verification to check whether these instruments are properly sterilized. They should be checked with mechanical methods, chemical indicators, and biological indicators (45). Chemical indicators are a special type of paper that change color when they are exposed to ethylene oxide gas, and the biological indicators are spores of *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. Atrophies*, and *B. Stearothermophilus* that are placed in the sterilizer load and after the completion of the sterilization cycle, these spores are removed and should be checked for their growth. If these spores germinate that shows instruments are not properly sterilized and require reesterilization (46). Due to its advantages, the ethylene oxide gas sterilization method has a bright future because it can sterilize all the instruments that are sensitive to heat, moisture, and radiation. It is an easy and inexpensive method everyone can used this, but that's required special attention due to its explosive nature.

Conclusion

Ethylene oxide (EO) gas sterilization is the one of the most effective and widely utilized methods for the sterilization of heat and moisture sensitive surgical instruments medical devices, pharmaceuticals products, and equipments. However, because of its carcinogenic properties, it must be used with extra caution.

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